

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : V.N.Sreekumar (2017), "SOCIAL PARTICIPATION OF ORTHOPEDICALLY HANDICAPPED IN THIRUVANANTHAPURAM DISTRICT", *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 5,May-2017), pp 20-26

SOCIAL PARTICIPATION OF ORTHOPEDICALLY HANDICAPPED IN THIRUVANANTHAPURAM DISTRICT

V.N.Sreekumar*

*Corresponding Author: Sri.V.N.Sreekumar,Lecturer in Social Work,
Department of Sociology,University of Kerala ,Kariavattam,Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

The aim of present research was to investigate the Social Participation of Orthopedically Handicapped in Trivandrum District. Further, the research was to examine the relation between Participation of disabled persons.

Method

The research design using for the study is Descriptive research design. The universe of the study is orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum district. Simple random sampling was used in this study. The data was collected from the respondent belonging to orthopedically handicapped using structured questionnaire.

Findings

It is observed that the mean value of civic participation of orthopedically handicapped persons are 12.67, mean value of developmental participation is 12.58, community participation is 9.36, institutional participation is 6.45 and family and peer group is 13.66.From that the participation of orthopedically handicapped in family and peer group is more. The study do not show any significant difference in social participation of orthopedically handicapped between men and women. Presence of occupation is dependent of social participation of orthopedically handicapped .Exposure in vocational training is independent of social participation of orthopedically handicapped. Membership in organisations is not much affected by social participation of orthopedically handicapped. The study reveals that educational qualification has no significant effect in social participation of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District. The study observed that rate of disability has significant effect in social participation of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum district.

Key Words: Social Participation, Orthopedically Handicapped

Introduction:

According to WHO impairment is defined as any loss or abnormality of psychological, physiological or anatomical structure or functions e.g. loss of foot, defective vision or mental retardation. An impairment may be visible or invisible, temporary or permanent, progressive or regressive.

Disability: because of any impairment, the affected person may be unable to carry out certain activities considered normal for his age, sex etc. this inability to carry out certain activities is termed disability a disability has been defined as "any restriction or lack of ability to perform an activities in the manner or within the range considered normal for a human being.

Handicap: As a result of disability, the person experiences certain disadvantages in life and is not able to discharge the obligations required of him and play the role expected of him in the society. This is termed

“handicap”, and is defined as “a disadvantage for a given individual, resulting from impairment or a disability that limits or prevents the fulfillment of a role that is normal.

The term orthopedic refers to impairment of the skeletal system, including the spine, other bones and associated muscles, orthopedic handicap are conditions of the skeletal system that limits a person’s abilities. Orthopedic handicaps include bone diseases such as Paget’s disease and orthogenesis imperfect, spinal cord injuries, nerve injuries such as brachial plexus palsy, and congenital conditions such as cerebral palsy and spina bifida.

Disability, however, is a human rights issue and it must be clearly realized by all that the disabled are an integral part of society and every effort must be made to involve them with the whole society. People with impairment feel disabled not because of their physical and/or mental handicaps but because of the barriers society chooses to put up to establish differences between the disabled and non-disabled. These barriers are the result of prejudice born out of ignorance and misconceptions. It is imperative that steps be taken to remove such barriers and eradicate widespread discrimination against men and women, children and adults suffering with disability. The disabled must also be offered wider and just opportunities to live independently in society with dignity and freedom to contribute to the richness of society in accordance with their skills and talents.

The disabled, like the non-disabled, expect full and active participation in all activities of their lives. Such participation can only become a reality if society removes these age-old barriers and increases the accessibility of the disabled to education, training and employment in a substantial measure. The lawmakers, and those who are implementing policies, must realize that people with disabilities want, deserve and are entitled to the same range of choices and lifestyles as the non-disabled. They should not be expected to live on crumbs of benefits thrown at them. The disabled deserve neither to be thrown in dustbins of society nor put on pedestals. They want to be treated as ordinary people that they actually are if seen without prejudice. Nothing substantial and of lasting value can be achieved without actively involving the disabled in their own struggle find dependence. During the past two decades, there has been considerable increase in professional interest concerning disability and rehabilitation in what may be called the developing world. The International Year of isabled Persons (IYDP) in 1981 played an important role in promoting such awareness, locally as well as internationally.

In the disability field, the concepts of 'participation' and 'social participation' have been made necessary since the 1990s in order to designate the terms and conditions of the performance of activities of daily living of an individual or a population within their life environment. The emergence of these concepts arose from the dynamics of various ideological changes. These concepts have justified a shift from the perspective of segregation, protection and special needs for people with body, function and behavior differences deemed deviant from normal standards or threatening for the surrounding community to one of exercise of fundamental human rights regardless of individual features.

Social participation is central to the quality of life and well-being, and is considered a prerequisite for the construction and maintenance of resources relevant to health, such as self-esteem, self-efficacy, and even support and social capital.

The problems faced by the orthopedically handicapped in our society are many and varied. They have a feeling of being unwanted or neglected by family members as well as by the society. The social attitude towards such people will naturally be one of patronizing and showing pity. Often they are regarded as inferior not only with respect to their physical limitations but also as total human beings.

The present world is instable and the disabled have to be given opportunities for their proper development. Today they want to participate in several programs as an active member than passive recipient. Social participation encompasses all activities outside people’s personal lives and the economy, or in other words paid work. The main aspect of social participation is social contact with friends, relatives and neighbors and involvement in other activities

Disables' social participation is the active engagement of people throughout their communities. Through social participation they acquire a sense of responsibility. They address real problems, can learn about the gravity of community problems and take action to address those problems.

Theoretical Back ground of the study

Although it may seem evident that the presence of a disability may pose a greater risk for low levels of social participation, the actual evidence is mixed and studies of youth are fairly limited. According to the National Longitudinal Transition Study-2 (NLTS2), a nationally representative sample of youth in the United States (US), secondary-school-age youth (13- 16 years) with a disability on average were substantially less likely to participate in community service or volunteer activities (41 per cent) than youth in the general population (73 per cent) (Wagner et al 2004). The level of involvement with friends and in extracurricular groups was also found to vary significantly according to the type of disability. Compared with the general population of youth with a disability, young people with a learning disability or speech impairment, for example, were among the most active; youth with hearing impairments were more likely to participate in group activities but had less frequent contact with friends; youth with emotional disturbances were less likely to be active group members; and youth with autism, multiple disabilities, or deaf-blindness had the lowest level of involvement with friends (Wagner et al 2004).

Another US based study on students (of elementary to high schools) with disability also found that participation in school activities (including social, recreational, communal, reative, civic and academic) varied significantly by the nature of the disability (Simeonsson et al 2000). The study found that students with attention or language and learning problems had the highest participation in these activities, followed by those with perception, hearing and vision problems, and students with emotional and behavior problems. Students with speech, neuro-muscular, intellectual development, and neurological problems had significantly lower participation, and participation of those with multiple disabilities was the lowest. The study, however, provided no comparison between students with and without disability.

There is also evidence from research conducted in other countries that disability may be a factor in social isolation. The European Commission, for example, concluded that disability was one of the major factors leading to social exclusion in the European Union (Finnish Disability Forum 2003). A study that they conducted examined accessibility of housing, culture, restaurant, cinemas, sports, clubs and other social activities and found that individuals with a disability were considerably more disadvantaged than those without a disability. The study noted that people with a disability commonly felt excluded from leisure and cultural activities. They also faced significant barriers in other areas of social life, such as participating in religious services. Important barriers for social participation included barriers in communication, attitudes, prejudice as well as physical and architectural barriers.

Similar barriers to social participation have been found in Australia. Australian Social Trends (ABS 2006a), for example, revealed that among all adults with disability (aged 18 years and over), one third of them did not leave their home as often as they would like; making participation in social activities outside the home more difficult. There were also large differences between disability groups in this respect; for instance, adults with a sensory or speech disability reported the highest proportion (70 per cent) of leaving home as often as they liked, while this was considerably lower among those with head injury, stroke or other brain damage (50 per cent) and especially those with a psychological disability (42 per cent) (ABS 2006a).

Other studies reported similar findings relating to the type of disability. For example, a report of the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) on children with juvenile arthritis, showed that sports participation and fitting in socially were among the most commonly reported difficulties in children with this particular condition (AIHW 2008). The report pointed out that these children could become socially isolated because of their difficulties in participating in a variety of physical activities. Two studies cited in the report, Ostensen et al (200) and Packham and Hall (2002), showed that young male adults with juvenile-onset arthritis

were more likely to live alone, and were less likely to be in a stable relationship. The report noted that there were no similar data in this respect in Australia.

Objectives of the study

To study the socio demographic profile of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District.
To study various component of Social participation of orthopedically handicapped
To analyse the social participation of orthopedically handicapped in terms of selected socio demographic variables.

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was tested and proved during the study tested and reached conclusion during the study.

There is a significant difference in social participation with respect to gender, educational status, exposure of vocational training, organisational membership, rate of handicap level of orthopedically handicapped.

Method

The research design used for the study is Descriptive research design. The universe of the study is orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum district. As per the data from several institutions there are 30148 orthopedically handicapped persons in Trivandrum district. Simple random sampling was used for this study. A total of 64 samples were collected from the respondent belonging to orthopedically handicapped using structured questionnaire.

Analysis and Discussion

This part is arranged as in three parts as per objectives like Socio demographic profile, Component of Social participation and analysis of Social Participation with Social demography of Orthopedically Handicapped

I. Sociodemographic profile of orthopedically handicapped

The sample for the study indicates that the orthopedically handicapped persons in the age of 20- 23 (29.7%), 24-27 (56.3%) and 28-30 (14.1%). It is observed that most of them come under 24-27 age group. 64.1% of the orthopedically handicapped persons are male category and 35.9% are female category. Again (40.6%) of the orthopedically handicapped persons completed higher secondary education, (46.9%) completed graduate and (9.4%) completed post graduate education and finally (3.1%) have technical education. 46.9% of the orthopedically handicapped persons have occupation and 53.1% have no occupation. (67.2%) of orthopedically handicapped are mild category, (29.7%) are moderate category and (3.1%) are severe category. From this table most of them are come under mild category.

(75.0%) of orthopedically handicapped completed vocational training and 16(25.0%) are not. From this it was observed that most of the respondents included in the sample are vocationally trained people. 95.3% of orthopedically handicapped persons are not an active member of any organization, only 4.7% are member of such organization. Coming to the voting right 90.6% of orthopedically handicapped persons are enjoying the right to vote and only 9.4% were not enjoying the voting right.

II. Component of Social participation

Table 1: components of social participation among Orthopedically Handicapped

Participation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Civic Participation	12.67	1.15
Developmental Participation	12.58	1.08
Community Participation	9.36	1.02
Institutional Participation	6.45	0.71
Family and Peer group	13.66	1.05

From the table it is observed that the mean value of civic participation of orthopedically handicapped persons are 12.67, mean value of developmental participation is 12.58, community participation is 9.36, institutional participation is 6.45 and family and peer group is 13.66. From that the participation of orthopedically handicapped in family and peer group is more.

III. Measure of associations of Social Participation with Social demography of Orthopedically Handicapped

Table.2: Mean, Standard deviation and t value of Social Participation with respect to social demography of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District.

Socio Demographic factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	t	Sig (2 tailed)
Gender				
Male	54.80	3.62	.26	.79
Female	54.57	3.32		
Occupation Status				
With Occupation	56.37	3.49	3.92	.000
Without occupation	53.26	2.82		
Vocational Training				
Got Training	54.60	3.66	.45	.65
Not Given	55.06	3.04		
Organisation Membership				
Active member	54.67	3.51	.02	.97
No Membership	54.72	3.52		

Gender and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that; the mean value of Social Participation of Male Orthopedically handicapped persons are (54.80) and that of females are (54.57). The result of the comparison of social participation shows, there is no significant difference between male and female ($t = .26, p > .05$) which indicates that gender status is independent of social participation among orthopedically handicapped.

Occupation status and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that; the mean value of Social Participation of Orthopedically handicapped persons With Occupation is (56.37) and that of Without occupation are (53.26). The result of the comparison of the significant difference of social participation between With Occupation and Without occupation ($t = 3.92, p > .001$) indicates that occupational status is dependent of social participation among orthopedically handicapped. The high mean value of OH with occupation indicates that they have a wider domain for the participation than the other category.

Vocational Training (VT) and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that; the mean value of Social Participation of Orthopedically handicapped persons with Vocational Training is (54.60) and without VT is (55.06). The result of the comparison of social participation shows, there is no significant difference between these groups ($t = .45, p > .05$) which indicates that Vocational Training Status is independent of social participation among orthopedically handicapped.

Organisational Membership and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that; the mean value of Social Participation of Orthopedically handicapped persons with Organisational membership is (54.67) and without Organisational Membership is (54.72). The result of the comparison of social participation shows, there is no significant difference between these groups ($t =$

.02, $p > .05$) which indicates that Organisational membership is independent of social participation among orthopedically handicapped.

Table .3: Mean, Standard deviation and One way ANOVA analysis of Social Participation with respect to social demography of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District.

	Mean	SD	F	Sig.
Education				
Higher secondary	53.9	3.87	0.98	.40
Graduate	55.1	2.82		
post graduate	56.1	2.40		
Others	54.0	9.89		
Disability				
Mild	55.9	2.9	12.62	.000
Moderate	52.7	3.2		
Severe	48.0	1.4		

Education and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that the mean value of higher secondary education of Orthopedically handicapped is (53.9), graduate is (55.1), post graduate is 56.1, and other educational level is (54.0). From the above results, post graduated persons have higher mean value of social participation. Analysis of the degree of association of social participation with educational status shows that ($F=0.98$ $p > .05$) there is no significant difference in social participation with respect to educational level of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District.

Rate of Handicapness and Social Participation

From the table it is observed that the mean value of mild level of orthopedically handicapped person is (55.9), moderate is (52.7) and of severe is (48.0). From this table it is clear that mild level of orthopedically handicapped has greater mean of social participation. Analysis of the degree of association of social participation with rate of handicapness ($F=12.62$, $p < .01$) indicates that Social participation of OH persons is highly significant difference with respect to rate of handicapness. In order to identify the groups with high significant difference post hoc analysis was used and the result is as follows.

Post-hoc Analysis

Category of Handicapness	Category	Mean difference	Sig
Mild.	Moderate	3.170	.000
	Severe	2.163	.7907

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

From the table the group mild and moderate shows significant mean difference (3.17) which implies that mild category shows high mean value (55.9) so this level of orthopedically handicapped has high participation than other moderate and severe category of handicapness.

Findings

It is observed that the mean value of civic participation of orthopedically handicapped persons are 12.67, mean value of developmental participation is 12.58, community participation is 9.36, institutional participation is 6.45 and family and peer group is 13.66. From that the participation of orthopedically handicapped in family and peer group is more. The study does not give any sign of significant effect of gender on the social participation of orthopedically handicapped. The study does not show any significant difference in social participation of orthopedically handicapped between men and women. Study also proves the presence of occupation is dependent of social participation of orthopedically handicapped and exposure in vocational training is independent of social participation of orthopedically handicapped. The results of the study did not

inclined to Membership in organisations, which is not much affected by social participation of orthopedically handicapped. The study reveals that educational qualification has no significant effect in social participation of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum District. The study again observed that rate of disability has significant effect in social participation of orthopedically handicapped in Trivandrum district.

References

ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics) (2004), Disability, ageing and careers: summary Of findings, ABS cat. No. 4430.0, ABS, Canberra

Bittman, M. (1999), Social participation and family welfare: the money and time cost of Leisure, SPRC Discussion Paper no. 95, Social Policy Research Centre, University of New South Wales, Sydney

Dewson, S., Aston, J., Bates, P., Ritchie, H. and Dyson, A. (2004), Post-16 transitions: A longitudinal study of young people with special educational needs: Wave two, Department for Education and Skills, Nottingham, UK.

DiPasquale, D. and Glaeser, E.L., (1999), 'Incentives and social capital: are homeowners better citizens?' Journal of Urban Economics, vol. 45, pp. 354-384

Hayes, A., Gray, M. Edwards, B. (2008), Social inclusion: origins, concepts and key themes, prepared for the Social Inclusion Unit, Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet, Australian Institute of Family Studies, Melbourne.